

Supramolecular Polymers: From Molecules to Materials

Bimalendu Adhikari*

IISER Mohali, Knowledge city, Sector 81, Manauli PO, SAS Nagar, Punjab 140306.
Email: badhikari@iisermohali.ac.in, Mob.: 9933898711

Supramolecular polymer is an important class of soft material because of its exceptional properties like reversibility and stimuli-responsiveness.¹ The unique properties of supramolecular polymers make this fascinating class of material to replace conventional covalent polymers and compare with biopolymers. I will present very recent achievement of light-induced dynamic control over foldability of supramolecular polymer inspired by protein foldability-unfolding. It has been achieved from naphthalene-azobenzene dyad that has an inherent tendency to form folded supramolecular polymer which is unfolded upon UV irradiation.² Ferrocene has been used an organometallic scaffold for the tuning of peptide conformation and higher order supramolecular assembly in which the redox state of ferrocene can regulate their material properties.³ Next, guanosine (G) is conjugated to stimuli-responsive moieties to form G-quartets which afford supramolecular polymers. These supramolecular polymers ultimately lead to the construction of responsive and self-healing hydrogels. Biology mimicking non-equilibrated supramolecular polymer is being constructed.

Keywords: Supramolecular polymer, Soft materials, Responsive materials

References

- 1) Aida et al., Science 335 (2012), 813.
2. Adhikari et al., Nat. Commun. 8 (2017), 15254.
3. Adhikari et al., Chem.–Eur. J. 21 (2015), 11560.